

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF LEARNING LANGUAGES STRATEGY-BASED INSTRUCTIONS

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Anotation: *In this article is about simple and productive ways of learning languages and very helpful instructions which can come handy in a language learning process are said*

Key words: *learning styles, VARK modul, sociocultural competence, visual learning, mind-mapping technology.*

Anotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'rganishning eng oddiy va samarali yo'llari va til o'rganish jarayonidagi eng foydali ko'rsatmalar haqida so'z yuritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *o'rganish usullari, VARK moduli, ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentsiya, ko'rish orqali o'rganish, "mind-mapping" metodi.*

A significant and very valuable development have appeared in the modern Uzbek system of education with the adoption of a new state educational standard. The educational standart novels the using of the highly advanced technologies and learning methods. This kind of developments can be helpful not only for education and learning processes but also for every walks of life.

Actually outdated methods of learning any kind of languages do not fully influence the improvement of creative and speech potential of students. But, on the other hand, the latest methods do not allow students to improve learning mechanisms by stimulating activation of mental processes but also develop cognitive skills. Learners tend to differ from one another in regarding with their age, characters, personality, temperaments and learning behaviours. If a teacher wants to achieve successful outcome, he or she should pay more attention to specific task which all students learn more easily. This kind of tasks normally selected based on students'

best learning styles. In fact, there are four main types of learning styles: -visual learners;

-auditory learner;

- kinesthetic learners

- reading/writing learner.

Additionally, these styles have been suggested by theory educationalist Neil Fleming in his VARK model of Student Learning. VARK an acronym for Visual, auditory, Kinesthetic, and Reading/Writing preference. The main idea of VARK models is to find out more beneficial learning methods. These models help stimulate students' motivation, attention, enhance metacognition. Visual learning styles also called as "spatial" learning style. It is easy for some students to learn new things on information visually by doodle information, making lists and taking notes. They can learn easy when the information is presented visually. As one example of this learning strategy, we can use "mind-mapping" method. This method was developed by English psychologist Tony Buson. This method directed to the various ways of learning as, drawing up plans, project development, general developments of mental abilities as well as activation of the associated speech when negative. This technology developed in the 60-70s of the twenties century but still performs one of the simple and at the same time effective ways of learning, summarize the material studied, display gained knowledge and develop logical thinking. Scientists have proven that information structured in this way is better absorbed which is especially important in working with pre-schoolers. In this method we can use prepared cards beforehand. For that, we must choose one theme, for example "fruits", prepare colourful and attractive cards which can grab visual learners' attention. By this cards students must learn the pictures translation, they draw in to their maps, towards finish to the another list. This will continue like that simultaneously.

The process of making a semantic card was joint creativity, and give the opportunity to children to be active participants in the comprehension of a new material, which together with a positive emotional perception, allowed to acquire the material of the lesson.

This, the benefits of using mental cards when learning is obvious. They make it possible to fully focus on the topic, purposefully for and enrich their vocabulary. Sensually know a significant number of objects and phenomena, make up the statement plan and develop a related speech. Reading and writing learners prefer learning materials through written words. They like to read books or articles, look up words in dictionaries write diaries and search the internet about almost everything. Additionally, this also best way of learning.

Actually, I am also reading and writing learner, and by this learning strategy, I can learn and remember everything easily and it is not natural to forget information which I learned by reading or writing. For this learning strategy, I found sociocultural competence as the best method. Sociocultural competence contributes to the realization of the ultimate goal of learning—the formation of the ability and readiness of the individual to intercultural dialogue, as well as its tolerant and positive perception of foreign language culture. All this allow to learners to successfully participate in the process of intercultural interaction. Furthermore, today it is important to teach not so much foreign languages, but intercultural communication. It should be noted that the use of foreign literature in teaching foreign languages makes the learning process more fun and high quality. By reading books in a foreign language students expand their vocabulary, knowledge of grammatical structure, develop translation skills, oral and written speech skills, they also introduce readers to specific aspects of the foreign language and cultures, which can help to enrich cultural background. This, we can conclude that fiction is an excellent source of sociocultural competence for students. Fiction by foreign authors is filled with description of the reality and realities of the country of the target language having great, historical, geographical, cultural, aesthetic value. Apart from that information which was given above there are some types of learning languages effectively. For instance, “think aloud” is an activity that is most effective while using metacognitive strategy that is the teacher brings a text and prepares questions related to the text students are going to read. After students are introduced the questions, they read the part of the text and answer the questions. Based on students’

responses teacher facilitates discussing which students explain why they have certain answers.

“Think, pair, share” is another activity to use while applying socio-active strategy, that is, the teacher asks students to think about the topic independently. They are then paired with another student to discuss this topic. After they both have spoken, the teacher asks learners to find another partner and talk about the same topic. At the end of this activity, the teacher tells students to share their partners’ ideas to the whole class.

In conclusion, since learning languages is becoming more and more popular in these days, especially among pupils and students, we should learn languages by using effective methods and strategies which can come handy for us during the learning processes.

References

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